

E-supplement

Lung and chest wall mechanics during PEEP inflation. II.

Gas distribution and regional lung mechanics.

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Calculation of full lung P/V curve from PEEP trial

Step 1: The lung P/V curve is obtained by plotting the end-expiratory transpulmonary pressure (PAW_{EE}) versus the end-expiratory lung volume at each PEEP level (Fig. 1). When lung elastance is determined as the difference in end-expiratory airway pressure divided by the difference in volume between two PEEP levels, this is the **true** lung elastance, as at end-expiration at a steady state PEEP/EELV equilibrium, the static **airway** pressure measured is equal to static **transpulmonary** pressure. This means that lung elastance is determined **directly** in contrast to the conventional method, where lung elastance is determined **indirectly** as the difference between respiratory system elastance and chest wall elastance. The direct method for determining lung elastance ($\Delta PAW_{EE}/\Delta EELV$) is extremely precise, as the end-expiratory airway pressure is maintained by the ventilator within mmH₂O of set value and reflects the mean transpulmonary pressure of the whole lung.

Fig. 1. As the end-expiratory transpulmonary pressure increases as much as PEEP is increased and the increase in end-expiratory lung volume following a PEEP increase is equal to $\Delta PEEP/EL$, a lung P/V curve can be obtained by plotting the end-expiratory airway pressure vs cumulative end-expiratory lung volume.

Step 2: As the end-expiratory and end-inspiratory lung P/V curves coincide and forms a common single lung P/V curve, the end-inspiratory transpulmonary pressure at each PEEP level can be

determined by solving the best-fit equation for the lung P/V curve for the end-inspiratory lung volume at each PEEP level (Fig. 2).

Fig.2. The end-inspiratory transpulmonary pressure, $PTPEI$, is determined by solving the equation for the lung P/V curve at the end-expiratory lung volume at each PEEP level. Blue arrows: tidal lung P/V curves. Black arrows point at the end-inspiratory pressure level.

Step 3: The end-inspiratory transpulmonary pressure at the highest PEEP level (16 cmH₂O) cannot be determined exactly as the lung P/V curve is non-linear and the chest wall elastance increases slightly PEEP step by PEEP step. Instead, the end-inspiratory transpulmonary pressure at the highest PEEP level can be estimated by extrapolating the ΔPPL from the ΔPPL at the four lower PEEP levels (fig. 3).

Fig. 3. The end-inspiratory transpulmonary P/V point at the highest PEEP level is estimated subtracting ΔPPL obtained by linear extrapolation of the ΔPPL of the four lower PEEP levels from the end-inspiratory airway pressure at the highest PEEP level. In this case, the extrapolated ΔPPL is 7.0 cmH₂O and as the PAWEI is 25.7 cmH₂O, the PTPEI is 18.7 cmH₂O.

By the calculation procedures described above, the static steady state end-expiratory and end-inspiratory pressure and volume points are obtained for the whole PEEP trial from end-expiration at the lowest PEEP level to end-inspiration of the highest PEEP level (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Transpulmonary pressure plotted vs volume during PEEP steps 0 – 4 – 8 – 12 – 16 cmH₂O. Open circles: End-expiratory P/V points. Filled circles: End-inspiratory P/V points. Note that end-expiratory and end-inspiratory p/V points are aligned on a single common lung P/V curve.

There is only one solution for calculation of the lung P/V curve where the tidal lung elastance, the end-expiratory lung elastance and the end-expiratory airway (respiratory system) elastance are equal and the end-expiratory and end-inspiratory transpulmonary pressure at a certain lung volume is the same, independent of whether this volume has been reached by tidal inflation or PEEP inflation. This can be illustrated by comparing the end-expiratory airway P/V curve (the lung P/V curve) with a lung P/V curve, where EL is determined conventionally as $(\Delta PAW - \Delta PES)/VT$ (fig. 5).

Fig. 5. The lung P/V curve calculated as described in figures 5-8, where the expiratory lung curve is indicated by a red dotted line and the tidal lung P/V curves indicated by dark blue arrows.

Left panel: Comparison with lung P/V curve where the increase in end-expiratory transpulmonary pressure is calculated as $\Delta EELV \times EL$, where EL is determined conventionally as $(\Delta PAW - \Delta PES)/VT$. Note that the tidal lung P/V curves (grey arrows) are aligned on a single lung P/V curve gray dotted line), but the end-expiratory transpulmonary P/V points are not coinciding with the end-expiratory airway P/V points, and the whole lung P/V curve, as a consequence, right shifted in relation to the end-expiratory airway P/V curve.

Right panel: Comparison where tidal lung P/V curves start from end-expiratory airway P/V points, where the tidal lung P/V curves are right shifted from the end-expiratory airway P/V curve. Consequently, tidal inspiratory lung P/V curves do not coincide with the end-expiratory airway P/V curve.

Regional lung P/V curves

As all pressures are measured/derived during steady state, static conditions, these pressures are the same in the whole lung from non-dependent to dependent regions. Consequently, gas will be distributed according to the regional elastic properties of the lung, both the tidal volume and ΔEELV . This is confirmed by using the EIT signal to divide the volume changes in the upper and lower half of the lung, which shows that end-expiratory and end-inspiratory transpulmonary P/V points are aligned on a common single lung P/V curve in both the non-dependent (ventral) and dependent (dorsal) half of the lung (Fig. 6).

Calculation of regional tidal volume and end-expiratory lung volume changes

First, the ratio of tidal impedance variation (ΔZ) to tidal volume (ml) is determined for each PEEP level. The tidal volume is constant, 420 ml, during the whole PEEP trial (Fig. 1).

Fig. 6. Global EIT registration in PEEP responder. The digits after the red brackets show the $\Delta Z/\text{ml}$.

The regional impedance change (ΔZ) related to tidal ventilation is registered from the regional EIT curves. The percentage ΔZ of each region at each PEEP level is calculated. The regional tidal volume for each PEEP level is calculated as percent ΔZ times tidal volume (ml) (Table 1).

VT	PEEP	$\Delta Z/VT$					$\% \Delta Z$				VT ml			
		R1	R2	R3	R4	$\Sigma \Delta Z$ R1-4	R1	R2	R3	R4	R1	R2	R3	R4
420	0	720	2630	1010	440	4800	0,15	0,55	0,21	0,09	63	230	88	39
420	4	550	2590	1130	530	4800	0,11	0,54	0,24	0,11	48	227	99	46
420	8	310	2450	1080	630	4470	0,07	0,55	0,24	0,14	29	230	101	59
420	12	390	2220	1160	730	4500	0,09	0,49	0,26	0,16	36	207	108	68
420	16	255	2000	1180	1000	4435	0,06	0,45	0,27	0,23	24	189	112	95

Table 1. Example of determining regional tidal ventilation. PEEP Responder patient. R = region of interest. R1: ventral ROI, R2: Mid ventral ROI, R3: mid dorsal ROI, R4: dorsal ROI. VT = tidal volume. ΔZ = tidal impedance variation.

The regional change in end-expiratory lung volume was calculated as the regional $\Delta Z/\Delta EELV$ divided by $\Delta Z/ml$ determined as the tidal impedance change divided by the tidal volume (Table 2).

PEEP	$\Delta Z/ml$	$\Delta Z/\Delta EELV$				$\Delta EELV$ ml			
		R1	R2	R3	R4	R1	R2	R3	R4
4	11,4	450	1670	430	230	39	146	38	20
8	11,4	600	2390	680	400	53	209	60	35
12	10,6	250	2980	1080	680	23	280	101	64
16	10,7	325	2870	1410	1110	30	268	132	104

Table 2. Regional $\Delta EELV$ linearized and converted to volume (ml) for each PEEP step by dividing $\Delta Z/\Delta EELV$ with $\Delta Z/ml$.

	PTP	VOL
EE0	0,0	0
EI0	6,0	420
EE4	4,0	245
EI4	8,4	665
EE8	8,0	611
EI8	11,5	1031
EE12	12,0	1109
EI12	15,0	1529
EE16	16,0	1679
EI16	18,7	2099

	Volume by EIT		
	PTP	Ventral	Dorsal
EE0	0,0	0	0
EI0	6,0	293	127
EE4	4,0	169	58
EI4	8,4	444	203
EE8	8,0	428	152
EI8	11,5	687	313
EE12	12,0	766	318
EI12	15,0	1010	494
EE16	16,0	1096	553
EI16	18,7	1309	759

Fig. 7. Lung P/V curves in a PEEP responder. Upper panels: Whole lung. Lower panels: Lung P/V curves in ventral and dorsal lung. End-expiratory (open circles) and end-inspiratory (closed circles) transpulmonary P/V points. Dashed vertical lines connect end-expiratory P/V points and whole vertical lines connect end-inspiratory transpulmonary P/V points in the whole lung and ventral and dorsal lung separately, as static pressures are the same everywhere